

Thermodynamic Stability Constants of 1-Naphthohydroxamic Acid with Copper (II), Zinc (II), Nickel (II) and Manganese (II)

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The thermodynamic metal ligand stability constants of 2-naphthohydroxamic acid (2-NHA) with Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} at 25° and 35° have been determined by pH titration technique. The order of stability found is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. The thermodynamic parameter were discussed.

THE analytical potentiality of 2-naphthohydroxamic acid is discussed by Vass and Yoe¹. The data on proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants will add to better understanding for its versatility in inorganic and organic analysis. A review of literature reveals that no data is available on metal ligand stability constants of 1-naphthohydroxamic acid (1-NHA). In the present communication the thermodynamic proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants of 1-NHA are described.

Experimental

Chemicals

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR and G.R. grades of B.D.H. and E. Merck, respectively.

Reagent and Apparatus

Carbonate free potassium hydroxide was prepared by the method of Vogel². The metal perchlorates were prepared by treating excess of carbonates with perchloric acid and concentration of metal ions in solutions were determined volumetrically³.

A Beckman digital pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrode was used for pH metric measurements.

Procedure

The details of procedure and calculation for proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants were described elsewhere⁴⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants for Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} with 1-NHA are summarised in Table I. The mole ratio of metal to 1-NHA was kept 1 : 10 in

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1-NAPHTHO HYDROXAMIC ACID WITH DIVALENT METAL IONS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Metal ion		log K_1	log K_2	log K_1K_2
Mn^{2+}	25°	3.50	2.30	5.80
	35°	3.30	2.09	5.39
Ni^{2+}	25°	4.65	3.85	8.50
	35°	4.44	3.66	8.10
Zn^{2+}	25°	5.05	3.90	8.95
	35°	4.85	3.70	8.55
Cu^{2+}	25°	5.91	4.60	10.51
	35°	5.70	4.42	10.12
H^+	25°	7.77	—	—
	35°	7.50	—	—

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR DIVALENT 1-NAPHTHOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Metal ion	Thermo-dynamic parameter	Temp.	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1K_2
Mn^{2+}	$-\Delta G^\circ$	25°	4.78	3.14	7.91
		35°	4.50	2.85	7.36
	$-\Delta H^\circ$	—	8.40	3.80	17.20
	$-\Delta S^\circ$	25°	12.14	15.63	31.16
		35°	12.65	19.30	31.92
Ni^{2+}	$-\Delta G^\circ$	25°	6.35	5.26	11.60
		35°	6.26	5.16	11.43
	$-\Delta H^\circ$	—	8.80	8.00	16.80
	$-\Delta S^\circ$	25°	4.86	9.19	14.09
		35°	8.24	9.21	14.18
Zn^{2+}	$-\Delta G^\circ$	25°	6.89	5.32	12.22
		35°	6.94	5.22	12.06
	$-\Delta H^\circ$	—	8.40	8.40	16.80
	$-\Delta S^\circ$	25°	5.06	10.33	15.36
		35°	5.06	10.32	15.38
Cu^{2+}	$-\Delta G^\circ$	25°	8.07	6.28	14.35
		35°	8.04	6.24	14.28
	$-\Delta H^\circ$	—	8.80	7.60	16.10
	$-\Delta S^\circ$	25°	2.45	4.43	5.87
		35°	2.47	4.11	6.55

$-\Delta G^\circ$ and $-\Delta H^\circ$ are in Kcal mole⁻¹ and $-\Delta S^\circ$ Cal.mol⁻¹deg⁻¹

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order to fulfil the maximum co-ordination number of metal ion. The maximum $\bar{n}$ value for all the complexes was 2, indicating a formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2.

The normal order of stability shown by Maley and Mellor⁷ and later Irving and Williams⁸ for divalent transition metal ions as

The stability constants of 1-NHA follows the order

The plot of $\log K_1$ vs the atomic number and ΔG° have the same order of stability. Beyond manganese the constants increase with increasing atomic number reaching to a maximum with $3d^8$ [Cu(II)]. A decrease is observed with $3d^{10}$ [Zn(II)] as follows.

The stability of copper complexes are much higher than can be expected from its ionic radius or electronegativity⁹. The extra stability of copper(II) complexes being square planer has been attributed to

Fig. 1. Variation of Stability Constants with ionisation potential of metal ions.

Jahn-Teller stabilization¹⁰. The $\log K_1$ values plotted against the respective overall ionisation potentials of Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Mn(II), (Fig. 1), to see the effect of electron affinity of the metal ions on the stability of the complexes they formed. A straight line obtained (Fig. 1), shows that the stability of the first complex ($\log K_1$) formed was directly proportional to central metal ion. The point correspond to Cu(II) complex is above the straight line shows that the copper possesses a higher degree of stability.

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